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DCXR functions at the plasma membrane.

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We describe here functions of a molecule DCXR with putative functions in inflammation. A major interactant of DCXR was sphingosine kinase Sphk1. Sphk1 catalyzes the reaction containing sphingosine and requiring phosphorylation to generate sphingosine 1 phosphate (SPP), and influences immunobiochemistry related to lipid mediators and inflammation. DCXR appeared to utilize the assistance of steroid biosynthesis enzymes *AKR1B1* and *AKR1B10*. We describe discovery of a relationship between DCXR function and the reductases *PECR* and *DECR*.